

Supplementary material – data extraction form

Post-discharge Care Interventions to Support Patient Recovery after Elective Degenerative Spine Surgery – a systematic review

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This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1).

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)	16-08-2022	
Name/ID of person extracting data	MDL	
Author(s)	Bizheva, K et al.	
Country	Republic of Macedonia	
Publication year	2016	
Title of article	Influence of Early Intensive Rehabilitation on Functional Mobility after Low Back Surgery	
Title of journal	Macedonian Journal of Medical Sciences	
Volume 15	Issue 4(4)	Pages 661-664
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)	Scientific article	

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 661-662
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify): Cohort study – although the study design is not specified.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants	All patients had similar impairments and functional limitations. The mean age of EG is 55.9 ± 13.8 , of CG is 58.3 ± 9.5 . The mean length of stay for EG is 3.9 ± 0.9 ; for CG is 3.6 ± 0.7 days. There were no significant differences in the age and	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 662

	length of hospital stay in both groups.				
Types of intervention	<p>Early goal-oriented physical therapy program in combination with educational booklet and standard physical therapy</p> <p>All patients performed daily physical therapy for 30 minutes with mild to moderate intensity achieving sitting position from the first day after surgery. Proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation for transfer positions, gait training (Table 1, 2) and an educational booklet with instructions (based on guidelines recommendations) on how to perform exercises and ADLs at home for one month after surgery (Table 3) were given to the patients of EG.</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>p. 661 title</p> <p>p. 662</p>
Types of comparison	The CG was on the standard physical therapy program and instructions on how to continue exercise at home and to resume daily activities gradually	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 662
Types of outcome measures	<p>Activity.</p> <p>Outcome measures include transfer from lying to sitting position, Timed Up and Go (TUG) test [3] and walking speed for a six-meter walk test [4]</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 662
INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>			

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	The influence of early goal-oriented physical therapy program in combination with educational booklet and standard physical therapy without written instructions	p. 661
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	Cohort study	
Unit of allocation (by individuals, cluster/groups or body parts)	Thirty patients, voluntarily attended and were treated in the Department of Neurosurgery at University Hospital Sofamed - Sofia was randomly divided into two groups, control group (CG n = 10) and experimental group (EG n = 20).	p. 661+662
Start date	<i>Not reported</i>	
End date	<i>Not reported</i>	

Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unclear	Not reported	
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Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)			
Setting (including location and social context)	Department of Neurosurgery	p. 661			
Inclusion criteria	Not reported				
Exclusion criteria	Not reported				
Informed consent obtained	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unclear	Not reported	

Intervention group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Experimental group	p. 662
No. randomised to group <i>(specify whether no. people or clusters)</i>	N=20	p. 662

Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)

All patients performed daily physical therapy for 30 minutes with mild to moderate intensity achieving sitting position from the first day after surgery. Proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation for transfer positions, gait training (Table 1, 2) and an educational booklet with instructions (based on guidelines recommendations) on how to perform exercises and ADLs at home for one month after surgery (Table 3) were given to the patients of EG.

p. 662

Table 1: Overview of the physical program

Steps	Goals	Activities
Preventing complications	Increase respiratory capacity -improvement of peripheral circulation	Breathing exercises/ combined with movement of the upper limbs, diaphragmatic breathing Abdominal drawing in manoeuvre
Take a sitting position	Self-moving in bed	Transfers and bed mobility exercises for upper and lower limbs in bed
Strengthening the spinal muscles	To increase the strength of muscles forming lumbar muscle corset.	abdominal exercises, isometric exercises, PNF
Training in walking	Improve posture Improve gait	Exercises for posture Training of gait Home exercise program (HEP)
Patient's education in ADL	Prevention and long-term self-care for the back	Healthy posture Balanced position of the spine and extremities

Table 2: Exercises and instructions

Exercises	Instructions	Time
Exercises in supine Neurodynamic glides Pivot does not twist with neutral spine with all transfers and bed mobility Posture principles for ADL	Training transfers to bed (until the drain is removed). The physical therapist helps patient to transfer from one position to the next, sit at the side of the bed without rotation (using techniques for convenience).	5-6 min. 2-3 times
Stabilisation exercises in supine-sit -standing with no weight Strengthening the muscles that support the lower back	The first verbalization is with or without a belt according to the intervention. Without pain	3-4 times 5-10 times
Training in ADL - lifting subjects, footwear, clothing - Golfer's lift and reacher	Patient's education focuses on the acquisition of information and technical skills and transition to self-fulfilling action, which facilitates patients, helping them to make decisions and take appropriate action when changes in their disease or condition [6].	10 min.
Walking to a place in countries of the right and left, Walking back, Skip the subject, Climbing down and up stairs	Reinforcement techniques transfers, sit and walking, training in walking, climbing down and upstairs and pick up the object from the floor [6]. The therapist helps with gait, balance and strengthening of lower and/or upper extremities.	10-15 min.

Table 3: Instructions to patients after discharge from hospital

N	ADL	Instructions
1.	Lying	Put a pillow under knees when lying on the back, and between knees when lying on one side.
2.	Getting up from bed	Sit in and get up from bed by first turning to one side - lying on the back, bend both legs and place one heel on the other knee
3.	Putting on shoes [6]	- in standing - tread on the shoe rack, or tread with one knee on the floor
4.	Sitting in a chair	During prolonged sitting before you stand up, perform several forward and backwards movements of the pelvis. Do not sit in one place for more than 20 minutes
5.	Getting up from a chair	When getting up from a chair body should bow forward, hands push from the hips. Hands can be used for support in sitting, too. Avoid low and soft armchairs and sofas.
6.	Getting subject [6]	To get subject without reaching or bending, it has to be on the level between hip and shoulder. When you need to take products from the refrigerator or stove, while bending the shoulders, you must slightly outsource back leg back and up, so that the body is not excessive bent.
7.	Lifting	Lifting the weight from the floor is through the squat, keep the weight close to the body
8.	Getting the objects above the head	Getting the objects above the head should not be done with tightening the body, but standing on something that will bring the subject to the level of the head.
9.	Washing dishes [6]	In activities when we lower the upper part of the body, we can carry the pelvis slightly back, with a little step one foot back
10.	Driving a car [6]	Avoid driving at least one week after surgery. While sitting in a car, do the seat back angle greater than 90 degrees. Avoid bending, especially when you get out of the car. Place a rubber mat on the floor to avoid sliding. If necessary, lay handles a convenient location to help with getting up from the toilet seat bath
11.	Getting a shower	
12.	Ironing	Ironing table should be at elbow level, you can use a chair to sit.
13.	Carrying	When carrying purchases, the weight is distributed evenly in both hands

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Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Experimental group	p. 662
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=10	p. 662
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Standard care: Physical therapy program and instructions on how to continue exercise at home and resume daily activities gradually.	p. 662

Outcomes

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)																																
Outcome name	Activity	p. 662																																
Time points reported	Not reported – only mentioned as 1 st , 2 nd , 3 rd assessment	p. 663, table 4																																
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	1) Transfer from lying to sitting, 2) Timed Up and Go test (TUG), 3) Walking speed for a six-meter walk test <p>Table 4: Outcomes for both groups</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Tests</th> <th>Group</th> <th>1st assessment Mean ± SD</th> <th>2nd assessment Mean ± SD</th> <th>3rd assessment Mean ± SD</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="2">Transfer (sec)</td> <td>EG</td> <td>9.1 ± 2.7</td> <td>6.1 ± 1.7</td> <td>4.3 ± 0.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CG</td> <td>9.1 ± 1.6</td> <td>7.7 ± 1.7</td> <td>5.5 ± 1.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="2">TUG (sec)</td> <td>EG</td> <td>20.1 ± 6.5</td> <td>14.9 ± 5.3</td> <td>8.8 ± 2.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CG</td> <td>19.8 ± 6.3</td> <td>16.5 ± 6.2</td> <td>11.8 ± 3.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="2">6 meters walk (m/s)</td> <td>EG</td> <td>0.4 ± 0.1</td> <td>0.6 ± 0.3</td> <td>1.0 ± 0.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CG</td> <td>0.4 ± 0.2</td> <td>0.6 ± 0.2</td> <td>0.8 ± 0.3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>SD- standard deviation; EG – experimental group; CG – control group.</p>	Tests	Group	1 st assessment Mean ± SD	2 nd assessment Mean ± SD	3 rd assessment Mean ± SD	Transfer (sec)	EG	9.1 ± 2.7	6.1 ± 1.7	4.3 ± 0.7	CG	9.1 ± 1.6	7.7 ± 1.7	5.5 ± 1.2	TUG (sec)	EG	20.1 ± 6.5	14.9 ± 5.3	8.8 ± 2.5	CG	19.8 ± 6.3	16.5 ± 6.2	11.8 ± 3.5	6 meters walk (m/s)	EG	0.4 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.3	1.0 ± 0.3	CG	0.4 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.3	p. 663
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	CG	0.4 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.3																														
	Favors intervention																																	

Follow-up

Follow-up	1 month	p. 662
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
Conclusion	<p>In conclusion, the survey revealed that early rehabilitation programs consisting of therapeutic exercises and written educational booklet after low back surgery improved transfer abilities and basic activities in one month. Further investigations should be made to assure the number of baseline variables which may influence the effectiveness of a physical therapy program and written instructions on functional mobility.</p> <p>CONCLUSION: The study revealed that early rehabilitation program consists of therapeutic exercises and written educational booklet after low back surgery improves transfer abilities and basic activities in one month.</p>	<p>p. 664</p> <p>p. 661, abstract</p>

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>